

PLACE OF WESTERN DIALECTS IN THE DIALECT SYSTEM

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The study of dialects is of great importance in exploring the dark pages of history. Dialectal vocabulary preserves the past of our people - its customs and traditions, daily life, lifestyle, economy, and ethnography. The classification of dialects and the position of the Western sub-dialects are discussed, and their area and boundaries are indicated. Dialects have always been resilient against the changes of societies and states throughout history. The mass migrations of the population related to political and economic events have had their impact on the geographical position of dialects and the area of isoglosses. The current spread of isoglosses of the Eastern, Western, and Southern dialects within the Northern sub-dialects of the Azerbaijani language is a result of migrations. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the area and character of the isoglosses alongside geographical principles in the classification of dialects.

Keywords: Western region, language, dialect, sub-dialect.

The Azerbaijani language has a rich dialect system. To date, the sub-dialects of our language have been sufficiently researched and grouped based on their geographical position and characteristic features. Dialect groups differ from each other based on their ancient features and the innovation centers of dialectal facts. Transitional sub-dialects, which bear the characteristics of two dialects, are located on the boundaries of dialects (or accents). The area of dialect facts is extensive and maintains its activity in communication process beyond the borders of our republic too. The Southern dialect has not lost its position in Southern Azerbaijan, and the Western dialect has also maintained its position in Türkiye, Georgia, and Iraq. This is an issue related to the history of our people. It arose as a result of the migrations of Turkic tribes, which historically played a significant role in the formation of our people and our language. Even centuries later, dialect facts bear witness to history. The study of dialects is of great importance in exploring the dark pages of history.

Dialects have always been resilient to the changes in societies and states throughout history. The mass migrations of the population related to political and economic events have had their impact on the geographical position of dialects and the area of isoglosses. The current spread of isoglosses of the Eastern, Western, and Southern dialects within the Northern sub-dialects of the Azerbaijani language is a result of migrations. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the area and character of the isoglosses alongside geographical principles in the classification of dialects. In Turkology, geographical principle has been given preference for a long time, and dialects have been classified based on this principle in the majority of Turkic languages (Turkish, Gagauz, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Altai, Tatar, Uyghur, etc.). The geographical principle was also taken as the basis in the initial periods of dialectological research in Azerbaijani linguistics.

M. Shiraliyev consistently dealt with the classification of Azerbaijani language sub-dialects. He grouped the sub-dialects geographically and divided them into five groups in his first classification. The scholar distinguished the Western accent under the name "Western group dialects," and included the Gazakh, Borchali, and Ayrim sub-dialects here, and he included the Kirovabad (present-day Ganja) and Karabakh sub-dialects in the "Middle group dialects." The division of Western dialects into two groups can be considered acceptable from a geographical perspective, but the Western and Middle group dialects do not possess distinct isoglosses from each other. M. Shiraliyev distinguished four dialect groups in the Azerbaijani language in his subsequent research. In this classification, the author eliminated the "middle group" and included the Ganja and Karabakh sub-dialects in the western group [11, p.18]. Since the geographical aspect was taken as the basis in this classification, the western sub-dialects were not fully covered.

Until the end of the last century, the position of dialects was primarily determined geographically, and linguistic features were not taken into account. On the other hand, all sub-dialects in the ethnogeography of Azerbaijan remained outside the division. Therefore, it became necessary to carry out a new division of dialects. The difference between E. Azizov's classification and previous ones is that the distinctive features set for the dialects are also taken into account alongside geographical principles. He took groups of sub-dialects and dialects as units of the dialectal division of the language and determined that there are three dialectal distinctions in our language. According to him, the western sub-dialects constitute the middle dialect.

This dialect covers the sub-dialects of the western and southwestern part of Azerbaijan between the Kura and Aras rivers (Gazakh, Ganja, Karabakh, Dashkasan, Gadabay, Kalbajar, Lachin) and some regions of Geor-

gia (Borchali, Marneuli, Bolnisi, Dmanisi). The Western dialect is divided into three sub-dialect groups: 1) Karabakh, 2) Gazakh-Borchali, 3) Ayrim sub-dialect (spread in Dashkasan, Gadabay, Kalbajar districts). The boundaries of the Western dialect are not limited to the territory of our republic. The Azerbaijani language sub-dialects used in the regions of the territories of Western Azerbaijan and the Republic of Georgia are within the scope of the Western dialect. The sub-dialects of Azerbaijanis who lived in the regions of Goycha, Shamshaddin, Pambak (Boyuk Garakilsa, Hamamli), and Lori (Mountain Borchali) in the territory of Western Azerbaijan correspond to the Gazakh-Borchali sub-dialects of the Western dialect [6, p.277].

Characteristic features of the Western dialects.

Here, the emergence of the characteristic features of three sub-dialect groups of the Western dialect—the Karabakh, Gazakh-Borchaly, and Ayrim dialects—and their role in the formation of the norms of our literary language are discussed.

The Karabakh dialect was formed on the basis of the language of the Dondarli, Qaramahmudlu, Qajar, Baharli, Hajili, Iyirmidordlu, Otuzikili, Shamshaddinli, Afshar, Gapanli, etc. tribes that settled in the territory of the Karabakh khanate in the Middle Ages. The Karabakh dialect rose to the level of a common language with the increase of the political and social influence of the region. This is clearly reflected in the language of M.P. Vagif, a prominent figure of the literary language in the 17th-18th centuries. In this regard, T. Hajiyev writes: "Molla Panah is originally from the Gazakh district. However, there are very few direct facts of the Gazakh dialect in his language... But the Karabakh dialect is represented relatively widely. Although some of these are also encountered in other dialects, they are considered more typical for Karabakh. According to the scholar, dialectisms such as *deyin* "for", *genə* "again", *çohrayı* "pink", *ləbiyin* "lips", *dadızdırmaq* "taste", *görkəzmək* "show", *sushar* "slide", *tazmak* "run", *gazmak* "look for", etc., which were active in the literary language of the period, belong to the Karabakh dialect.

Although the territorial-administrative division of Karabakh has been changed in recent times, it has not seriously affected the dialect. Currently, this dialect covers 15 districts of our republic and they differ only slightly from each other. The majority of the Karabakh sub-dialects have been studied by various scholars (T. Hajiyev, S. Behbudov, I. Guliyev, P. Aghayev). Based on the conducted research, it is possible to summarize the characteristics of the Karabakh dialect as follows: Strength of the sound "a" in the middle of a word: *yavan*, *yavash*, *javan*, *hayva*; Strength of the sound i at the beginning of a word: *ilan*, *ilkhi*, *ildirim*, *sichan*; e~ə alternation: *əv* (home), *səvgi* (love), *çəvir* (turn); ə~a alternation: *qiyamat* (disaster), *Heydar*, *jiyar* (lung), *khavar* (east); Strength of the sound b at the beginning of a word: *biçin* (harvesting), *balta* (ax), *budakh* (branch); Strength of the sound d at the beginning of a word: *dish* (rock), *dush* (narrow), *dustakh* (prisoner); Strength of the sound y in the middle of a word: *iyənə* (middle), *duyu* (rice), *duyma* (button); q~x(kh) alternation: *qururukh* (building), *qoruyurukh* (protecting), *uzakh* (far), *qonqakh* (pasture), *yeylakh* (seasonal

mountain pasture), *chirakh* (light); k~y alternation: *tay* (alone), *aysiy* (missing), *yeyay* (let's eat); Addition of the sound y at the beginning of a word: *yenış* (descent), *yalov* (fire), *yuca* (high), *yüzük* (ring); Observance of vowel harmony: *okhshuyuram* (I resemble), *durmuyum* (I don't get up), *tokhumluyurdu* (He was seeding); Use of case and possessive suffixes in four variants; Use of the -nı suffix in the accusative case; Second person of the possessive category: *ataŋa*, *ataŋıza*, *nəvəŋizə*; Plural form of second person at the person category: *bavasıŋız*, *öladıŋız*; Use of the ability mood form as *aləlmədim*, *gələlmədim*; Use of the demonstrative pronouns *bular*/ *bullar*, *əynə*- *bəynə*/ *ənə*-*bənə*; Use of the conjunction *ki* in 4 variants: *kı*, *ki*, *ku*, *kü*; These features are characteristic of the Karabakh sub-dialects.

The characteristic features of the Gazakh-Borchali sub-dialects historically emerged on the basis of the languages of various tribes that lived in these territories. It is possible to summarize the features of these sub-dialects as follows: a~u alternation: *yuvan*, *yuvaş*, *cuvan*; e~ö alternation: *öy*, *söyü*, *çöyür*; i~ı alternation: *sıçoul*, *sıçan*; Strength of the sound o in the middle of a word: *qohum*, *ov*, *qovurma*; Use of the velar ŋ sound: *təŋək*, *soŋra*; d~t alternation: *tiş*, *tüş*, *tustax*; Use of the accusative case suffix -yı: *qapıyı*, *arabıyı*, *danıyı*; Use of the second person of the possessive category in the forms *ataŋa*, *ataŋıza*, *nəvəŋizə*, etc.

The evolution of the literary language is connected to the expansion of the dialect's social function and linguistic possibilities. As a result of political-economic and literary-cultural development, the communicative function of the dialect expands, and it becomes a supradialect. Like in world languages, the Azerbaijani literary language has also passed through these stages. Over time, facts from other dialects can also become norms in the literary language. They are parallelly used with the feature of common communication language, then it gains the right of usage in the language. Thus, the norms of the literary language are formed based on the features of not one, but several dialects.

However, the supremacy of the common communication language has been preserved throughout all periods. The development of the Azerbaijani literary language shows that the position of common communication language also changes with the change of political-economic and cultural centers. The Azerbaijani literary language was based on the Shirvan dialect in the 13th-14th centuries, in the 15th-17th centuries on the Tabriz dialect, in the 18th century on the Karabakh dialect, and in the 19th-20th centuries on the speaking of the population of Baku city, which included representatives of all dialects [10, p.286]. Although there are various opinions regarding the common communication language of our modern literary language, according to M. Shiraliyev, it is the Baku and Shamakhi dialects [15, p.83].

Hajiyev justifies the transition from common communication language to literary language as follows: "In the case of a common communication language, the language-dialect of the city or province considered the economic-political and scientific-cultural center of the country comes into play. ...the common communication language generalizes features of a supradialectal character from other dialects, thereby enriching itself

further. The common communication language expands lexically at the expense of other dialects, but preserves its own phonetic-pronunciation and morphological characteristics. Although the literary language begins its activity within the framework of one dialect, it gradually becomes enriched with supradialectal features and moves away from being a dialect [7, p.21-12].

The idea that the common communication language dialect is formed based on the features of not one, but several dialects has been noted in the research of M. Shiraliyev, M. Jahangirov, S. Jafarov, A. Jafar, and N. Gaziyeva. According to N. Gaziyeva's conclusion, all dialects have a role in the formation of the phonetic and lexical norms of the modern literary language. Regarding the grammatical dialect base, especially the morphological norms largely correspond to features belonging to the western group dialects (primarily with the Karabakh dialects) [9, p.129].

As can be seen, the western sub-dialects have passed through a long historical development path; phonetic, lexical, and grammatical dialectal differences emerged based on the specific linguistic features of the ancient Turkic tribes that participated in the ethnic roots of our people, and played an important role in the formation and enrichment of the literary language.

Individual words in the Western sub-dialects.

Dialectisms that are not used in the literary language and are characteristic of this region are investigated. These dialectisms are replaced by homonyms or synonyms in the Kars sub-dialects; for example: *adakh* "a child's first steps", *aghirix* "heavy items left in the village when migrating to the summer pasture, household equipment sent ahead when migrating to the summer pasture", *banda* "a cluster of grapes tied together with tobacco leaves or stems strung on a thread", *basikh* "a passage laid over a fence", *aghmakh* "to go up, to rise", *chatal* "adjacent to each other (fruit)", two-headed, the place where two streams merge, a cocoon wound together by two worms", *chanchana* "fog", *chiya* "the cream of raw milk, the surface", *chatan* "reed", *bitiriji* "courier, a person who distributes papers in an office", *alamanchi* "thief, robber", *badakh* "a string tied to the legs of birds or animals to prevent them from running far, a support", *dashgir* "small stone fragments in grain, a coarse sieve" and so on.

The area of the Western dialect of the Azerbaijani language is extensive. It covers the regions of Gazakh, Karabakh, Ganja, Dashkasan, Gadabay, Kalbajar, and

Lachin. The boundaries of this dialect are not limited to the territory of our republic. The sub-dialects of the regions of Goycha, Shamsaddin, Pambak (Boyuk Qarakilsa, Hamamli), Loru (Mountain Borchali) in the territory of Western Azerbaijan, as well as the Borchali, Mameuli, Bolnisi, and Dmanisi districts of the Republic of Georgia, are also within the scope of the Western dialect.

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